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Review Article

UPLC-MS Method Development and Validation for Fluticasone Propionate: A Comprehensive Review

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ABSTRACT

The development and validation of a UPLC-MS (Ultra-Performance Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry) method for Fluticasone Propionate are crucial for ensuring accurate, sensitive, and reliable analysis in various samples, such as plasma and nasal sprays. This method aims to provide precise measurements of drug concentrations, detect low levels for pharmacokinetic studies, and distinguish Fluticasone Propionate from other compounds and impurities. The scope includes creating robust techniques for detecting and quantifying the drug in complex biological matrices, employing solid-phase extraction for effective isolation, and ensuring high sensitivity and selectivity. Comprehensive validation is essential for accuracy, precision, reproducibility, and stability. The importance of this method lies in its ability to ensure the drug's quality, safety, and efficacy, meeting regulatory requirements and supporting routine quality control. Fluticasone Propionate, a synthetic corticosteroid, is effective in managing various inflammatory and allergic conditions, improving patient quality of life. UPLC-MS is an ideal method for its analysis due to its high sensitivity, selectivity, speed, accuracy, and versatility, making it a robust tool for ensuring the safety and efficacy of pharmaceutical products.

INTRODUCTION

Fluticasone Propionate Overview:

Fluticasone Propionate is a synthetic glucocorticoid with potent anti-inflammatory Properties. It is highly selective for the glucocorticoid receptor, minimizing activity at other Steroid receptors. Fluticasone propionate

works by reducing inflammation and immune responses. It Achieves this by inhibiting multiple types of cells (e.g., mast cells, eosinophils) and Mediators (e.g., histamines, cytokines) involved in inflammation^[1,2].

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Fig. 1. Fluticasone Propionate

Uses in Treatments :

1. **Asthma:** It is commonly used as an inhaler for long-term management, helping to Prevent asthma attacks by reducing airway inflammation^[3].
2. **COPD:** It helps manage symptoms and Exacerbations by decreasing inflammation in the airways^[4].
3. **Allergic Rhinitis:** As a nasal spray, it alleviates symptoms like nasal congestion, Sneezing, and runny nose^[5].
4. **Skin Conditions:** Topical forms are used to treat inflammatory skin conditions such as Eczema and psoriasis^[6].

Importance of Accurate Quantification:

Accurate quantification of fluticasone propionate is crucial to ensure therapeutic efficacy And minimize side effects. Over- or under-dosing can lead to inadequate symptom control Or increased risk of side effects, such as adrenal suppression or local irritation^[7].

Challenges in Analysis:

1. **Complex Sample Matrices:**
 - i. **Biological Matrices:** Blood, urine, and tissue samples contain various interfering Substances that can complicate the analysis^[8].
 - ii. **Pharmaceutical Formulations:** Excipients and other active ingredients can interfere With the detection and quantification of corticosteroids^[9].

2. **Low Concentration Levels:** Corticosteroids are often present in very low concentrations, requiring highly Sensitive analytical methods to detect and quantify them accurately^[8].
3. **Stability Issues:** Corticosteroids can be unstable and degrade over time, especially under certain conditions like exposure to light, heat, or varying pH levels^[9].
4. **Analytical Method Development:** Developing robust analytical methods that can accurately quantify corticosteroids In the presence of various interfering substances is challenging. Techniques like LCMS/MS and GC-MS are often used but require extensive method Development and validation^[8,9].
5. **Sample Preparation:** Effective sample preparation is crucial to remove interfering substances and Concentrate the corticosteroids. Techniques like Solid-Phase Extraction (SPE) and Liquid-Liquid Extraction (LLE) are commonly used but can be time-consuming and Require optimization^[8].
6. **Regulatory Requirements:** Ensuring compliance with regulatory standards for accuracy, precision, and Sensitivity adds another layer of complexity to the analysis^[9].
7. **Matrix Effects:** The presence of other substances in the sample can affect the ionization efficiency In mass spectrometry,

leading to matrix effects that can skew results^[8].

Why UPLC-MS?

UPLC-MS is often Chosen over other analytical methods due to several key advantages:

1. Speed:

1. **Faster Analysis:** UPLC uses smaller particle sizes (sub-2-micron) and operates at Higher pressures, significantly reducing analysis time compared to traditional HPLC^[10].
2. **High Throughput:** The rapid separation capabilities of UPLC allow for high-throughput Analysis, making it ideal for laboratories with large sample volumes^[11].

2. Sensitivity:

1. **Enhanced Detection:** The combination of UPLC with MS provides superior sensitivity, Enabling the detection of low-abundance compounds in complex matrices^[12].
2. **Lower Limits of Detection:** UPLC-MS can achieve lower limits of detection and Quantification, which is crucial for trace analysis in pharmaceutical and environmental Samples^[13].

3. Resolution:

1. **Improved Separation:** UPLC offers higher resolution due to the use of smaller particle Sizes, which enhances the separation of closely related compounds^[12].
2. **Sharper Peaks:** The narrower peak widths in UPLC result in better peak capacity and Resolution, allowing for more accurate identification and quantification of analytes^[14].

4. Efficiency:

1. **Higher Efficiency:** The increased efficiency of UPLC leads to better separation performance and reduced solvent consumption, making it more cost-effective and environmentally friendly^[14].

2. **Reproducibility:** UPLC-MS provides high reproducibility and precision, which is essential for reliable analytical results^[14].

5. Versatility:

1. **Wide Range of Applications:** UPLC-MS is versatile and can be used for a variety of applications, including drug development, metabolomics, proteomics, and environmental Analysis^[13].
2. **Complex Sample Analysis:** It is particularly effective for analyzing complex biological and pharmaceutical samples, where high sensitivity and resolution are required^[13].

6. Data Quality:

Enhanced Data Quality: The combination of high resolution, sensitivity, and Speed results in superior data quality, reducing the need for repeated analyses and Improving overall productivity.

UPLC-MS Method Development:

Mobile Phase Optimization:

1. Choice of Solvents^[15]:-

1. **Water:** Commonly used as the aqueous component of the mobile phase. It is often combined with organic solvents to create a gradient.
2. **Acetonitrile:** Preferred organic solvent due to its low viscosity, high elution strength, and compatibility with mass spectrometry. It provides sharp peaks and good resolution.
3. **Methanol:** Another organic solvent option, though it has a higher viscosity than acetonitrile. It can be used to adjust the polarity of the mobile phase.
4. **Ammonium Formate:** Often used in positive ion mode due to its volatility and compatibility with MS detection. It helps maintain a stable pH and improves peak shape.
5. **Ammonium Acetate:** Suitable for both positive and negative ion modes. It provides good buffering capacity and is also MS-compatible.

6. Formic Acid: Commonly used to adjust the pH of the mobile phase. It enhances ionization efficiency in MS and improves peak shapes.

2. Impact of pH and Composition on Retention and Resolution:-

1. pH Control: The pH of the mobile phase significantly affects the ionization state of analytes, which in turn influences their retention and resolution. For example, acidic pH can improve the retention of basic compounds by keeping them in a non-ionized state^[16].
2. Retention: Non-ionized forms of analytes generally have better retention on reversed-phase columns. For acids, this means lower pH, and for bases, higher pH^[17].
3. Resolution: Proper pH adjustment can enhance the separation of closely related compounds. For instance, an alkaline pH can improve the resolution of compounds that are poorly separated at acidic pH^[16].
4. Buffer Concentration: The concentration of the buffer can also impact the retention and resolution. Higher buffer concentrations can improve peak shapes but may also increase the baseline noise in MS detection^[16].

Stationary phase:

C18 Columns:

1. Versatility: C18 (octadecyl) columns are the most commonly used due to their broad applicability. They provide excellent retention for various non-polar to moderately polar compounds.
2. Hydrophobic Interactions: The long carbon chain of C18 offers strong hydrophobic interactions, making it ideal for separating non-polar analytes.
3. Stability: C18 columns are stable across a wide pH range, which is beneficial for method development and robustness^[9].

Mass Spectrometry Parameters for Fluticasone Propionate:

1. Ionization Mode:

1. Positive Ion Mode: Fluticasone propionate is typically analyzed in positive ion mode due to its ability to form positively charged ions, which are more stable and easier to detect.
2. Negative Ion Mode: While less common, negative ion mode can be used for specific metabolites or when analyzing in a dual-mode setup.

2. Mass Range Selection:

Mass Range: For fluticasone propionate, the mass range is typically set to detect the parent ion at m/z 501.3 and its major fragment ions. This ensures accurate quantification and identification.

3. Source Parameters:

1. Capillary Voltage: Typically set between 3.0 to 4.5 kV in positive ion mode to ensure efficient ionization.
2. Desolvation Temperature: Usually set around 300-400°C to aid in the evaporation of the solvent and improve ionization efficiency.
3. Desolvation Gas Flow: Often set to 600-800 L/h to assist in the desolvation process and enhance signal stability.
4. Cone Voltage: Adjusted to 20-40 V to optimize the transmission of ions into the mass analyzer.

Method Validation For Fluticasone Propionate:

Specificity:

1. Definition: The ability of the method to unequivocally assess the analyte in the presence of components such as impurities, degradation products, and matrix components.
2. Approach: Analyze spiked samples containing known impurities and excipients to ensure that fluticasone propionate can be accurately detected and quantified without interference. This involves comparing the chromatograms of spiked and unspiked samples to check for co-eluting peaks^[18].

Linearity:

1. Definition: The method's ability to obtain test results that are directly proportional to the analyte concentration in the sample within a given range.
 2. Approach: Prepare calibration curves using standard solutions of fluticasone propionate at different concentrations. Typically, a range of 5-7 concentrations is used to establish linearity. The correlation coefficient (R^2) should be close to 1 (e.g., >0.99) to confirm linearity^[18,19].
- Definition: The lowest amount of analyte that can be quantitatively determined with suitable precision and accuracy.
 - Approach: Determined similarly to LOD, but with a signal-to-noise ratio of about 10:1^[19,20].

Robustness:

1. Definition: The ability of the method to remain unaffected by small, deliberate variations in method parameters.
2. Approach: Test minor variations in parameters such as flow rate, column temperature, and mobile phase composition. Evaluate the impact on retention time, peak area, and resolution^[19].

Stability:

1. Definition: The ability of the analyte to remain unchanged during sample storage and analysis.
2. Approach: Assess the stability of fluticasone propionate in the sample matrix over time under various conditions (e.g., room temperature, refrigerated, frozen). Analyze samples at different time points to determine any degradation^[19].

Application To Real Samples:

Pharmaceutical Formulations:

Quantification in Tablets, Inhalers, etc^[18].

1. Sample Preparation:
 - Tablets: Crush the tablets to a fine powder and dissolve in a suitable solvent (e.g., methanol or acetonitrile). Filter the solution to remove any undissolved particles.
 - Inhalers: Extract the active ingredient by dissolving the contents in a solvent. This may involve shaking or sonication to ensure complete extraction.
2. Extraction and Cleanup:

Solid-phase extraction (SPE) or liquid-liquid extraction (LLE) are used to isolate fluticasone propionate from the sample matrix. This step helps to remove excipients and other interfering substances.

Accuracy and Precision:

1. Accuracy:
 - Definition: The closeness of the test results obtained by the method to the true value.
 - Approach: Assess by spiking known amounts of fluticasone propionate into the matrix and calculating the % recovery. Acceptable recovery is typically within 98-102%.
2. Precision:
 - Definition: The degree of agreement among individual test results when the method is repeatedly applied to a homogeneous sample's multiple samplings.
 - Intra-day Precision: Perform multiple analyses of the same sample within a single day and calculate the %RSD.
 - Inter-day Precision: Perform the same analysis on different days and calculate the %RSD. Acceptable %RSD is usually less than 2%^[18,19].

Sensitivity:

1. Limits of Detection (LOD):
 - Definition: The lowest amount of analyte that can be detected, but not necessarily quantified, under the stated experimental conditions.
 - Approach: Typically determined by analyzing samples with decreasing concentrations of the analyte until the signal-to-noise ratio is about 3:1.
2. Limits of Quantification (LOQ):

3. UPLC-MS Analysis:

- Inject the prepared sample into the UPLC-MS system. The optimized method parameters (e.g., mobile phase composition, flow rate, column temperature) will ensure efficient separation and accurate quantification.
- Monitor the specific m/z value for fluticasone propionate (e.g., m/z 501.3) and its major fragments to confirm the presence and concentration of the analyte.

4. Calibration and Quantification:

Use calibration curves prepared from standard solutions of fluticasone propionate to quantify the amount in the pharmaceutical formulation. Ensure that the calibration range covers the expected concentration in the sample.

5. Validation:

Validate the method for specificity, linearity, accuracy, precision, sensitivity, robustness, and stability as discussed earlier. This ensures that the method is reliable and reproducible for routine analysis.

Biological Samples:

Application in Blood or Plasma^[21].

1. Sample Collection and Preparation:

- Collect blood or plasma samples using standard procedures. Store samples at appropriate temperatures to prevent degradation.
- Prepare the samples by protein precipitation, SPE, or LLE to isolate fluticasone propionate from the biological matrix. This step is crucial to remove proteins and other interfering substances.

2. Extraction and Cleanup:

Use SPE or LLE to concentrate and purify fluticasone propionate from the biological matrix. This step enhances the sensitivity and accuracy of the analysis.

3. UPLC-MS Analysis:

- Inject the prepared biological sample into the UPLC-MS system. The optimized method

parameters will ensure efficient separation and accurate quantification.

- Monitor the specific m/z value for fluticasone propionate and its major fragments to confirm the presence and concentration of the analyte.

4. Calibration and Quantification:

Use calibration curves prepared from standard solutions of fluticasone propionate in a matrix-matched solution (e.g., blank plasma spiked with known concentrations of the analyte). This accounts for matrix effects and ensures accurate quantification.

5. Validation:

Validate the method for specificity, linearity, accuracy, precision, sensitivity, robustness, and stability in the biological matrix. This ensures that the method is reliable and reproducible for clinical or pharmacokinetic studies.

Challenges And Limitations In Uplc-Ms Method Development:

Developmental Challenges^[9,22,23]:

1. Column Selection:

- i. Variety of Columns: Selecting the right column can be challenging due to the wide variety of available options (e.g., C18, C8, phenyl, HILIC). Each column type offers different selectivity and retention characteristics.
- ii. Compatibility: Ensuring the chosen column is compatible with the mobile phase and analyte properties is crucial. For instance, C18 columns are widely used for non-polar compounds, but may not be suitable for highly polar analytes.
- iii. Optimization: Fine-tuning the column parameters (e.g., particle size, pore size) to achieve optimal separation and resolution requires extensive experimentation and can be time-consuming.

2. Mass Spectrometry Settings:

- i. Ionization Mode: Choosing between positive and negative ionization modes can be complex, as it depends on the chemical nature of the analyte and the matrix. Fluticasone propionate typically requires positive ion mode, but this may not be ideal for all related compounds.
 - ii. Source Parameters: Optimizing source parameters such as capillary voltage, desolvation temperature, and gas flow rates is critical for achieving high sensitivity and reproducibility. This process often involves iterative testing and adjustments.
 - iii. Mass Range Selection: Determining the appropriate mass range to capture all relevant ions without compromising sensitivity or resolution can be challenging, especially in complex matrices.
- i. Environmental Factors: UPLC-MS methods can be sensitive to minor variations in environmental conditions (e.g., temperature, humidity), which can affect reproducibility and accuracy.
 - ii. Matrix Effects: The presence of complex matrices can lead to ion suppression or enhancement, impacting the accuracy and sensitivity of the method.

Opportunities for Future Improvements^[25]:

1. Cost Reduction:

- i. Technological Advances: Continued advancements in UPLC-MS technology could lead to more cost-effective systems and consumables, making the technology more accessible.
- ii. Shared Resources: Implementing shared instrumentation facilities can help distribute the cost burden and provide access to advanced technologies for smaller laboratories.

2. Simplification of Method Development:

- i. Automated Optimization: Developing software tools for automated method optimization can reduce the time and expertise required for method development.
- ii. Standardized Protocols: Creating standardized protocols for common applications can streamline the method development process and improve reproducibility.

3. Enhanced Robustness:

- i. Improved Instrumentation: Enhancing the robustness of UPLC-MS systems to withstand environmental variations can improve method reliability.
- ii. Matrix Management: Developing better techniques for managing matrix effects, such as advanced sample preparation methods or matrix-matched calibration, can enhance accuracy and sensitivity.

Limitations of the Method^[24]:

1. Cost:

- i. Equipment: UPLC-MS systems are significantly more expensive than traditional HPLC systems. The high initial investment and maintenance costs can be a barrier for some laboratories.
- ii. Consumables: The cost of UPLC columns, solvents, and other consumables is higher compared to HPLC, adding to the overall operational expenses.

2. Complexity:

- i. Technical Expertise: Operating and maintaining UPLC-MS systems require specialized training and expertise. This can limit the accessibility of the technology to laboratories with skilled personnel.
- ii. Method Development: The complexity of method development, including the optimization of multiple parameters, can be time-consuming and requires a deep understanding of both chromatography and mass spectrometry.

3. Sensitivity to Variations:

Regulatory Considerations For Method Validation:

ICH Q2(R1) Guidelines for Method Validation^[26,27]:

The International Council for Harmonisation (ICH) Q2(R1) guidelines provide a comprehensive framework for the validation of analytical procedures. These guidelines emphasize the importance of demonstrating that an analytical method is suitable for its intended purpose. Key parameters include:

1. Specificity:

- Definition: The ability to assess unequivocally the analyte in the presence of components such as impurities, degradation products, and matrix components.
- Approach: Ensure that the method can accurately identify and quantify fluticasone propionate without interference from other substances.

2. Linearity:

- Definition: The ability to obtain test results that are directly proportional to the analyte concentration in the sample.
- Approach: Prepare calibration curves over a specified range and ensure a high correlation coefficient ($R^2 > 0.99$).

3. Accuracy:

- Definition: The closeness of the test results obtained by the method to the true value.
- Approach: Assess by spiking known amounts of fluticasone propionate into the matrix and calculating the percentage recovery.

4. Precision:

- Definition: The degree of agreement among individual test results when the method is

applied repeatedly to multiple samplings of a homogeneous sample.

- Intra-day Precision: Perform multiple analyses within a single day and calculate the %RSD.
 - Inter-day Precision: Perform the same analysis on different days and calculate the %RSD.
- #### 5. Sensitivity:
- Limits of Detection (LOD): The lowest amount of analyte that can be detected but not necessarily quantified.
 - Limits of Quantification (LOQ): The lowest amount of analyte that can be quantitatively determined with suitable precision and accuracy.

6. Robustness:

- Definition: The ability of the method to remain unaffected by small, deliberate variations in method parameters.
- Approach: Test minor variations in parameters such as flow rate, column temperature, and mobile phase composition.

7. Stability:

- Definition: The ability of the analyte to remain unchanged during sample storage and analysis.
- Approach: Assess the stability of fluticasone propionate in the sample matrix over time under various conditions (e.g., room temperature, refrigerated, frozen).

These guidelines ensure that the analytical method is reliable, reproducible, and suitable for its intended purpose^[26,27].

Table 1: The results of UPLC-MS method development and validation for fluticasone propionate^[18].

Parameter	Result
Specificity	High specificity achieved using selective MS/MS transitions.
Linearity	Linear range of 1.009-200.45 pg/mL with a correlation coefficient >0.99.
Sensitivity	Lower limit of quantitation (LLOQ) of 1 pg/mL.
Accuracy	Accuracy within 85-115% of the nominal concentration.

Precision	Coefficient of variation (CV) < 15% at all QC levels.
Recovery	Recovery rates between 80-120%.
Matrix Effect	Minimal matrix effects observed.
Stability	Stable under various storage conditions.

Future Directions:

Potential for Broader Applications^[9,28]:

1. Application to Other Corticosteroids:

1. Similar Molecules: The developed UPLC-MS method for fluticasone propionate can be adapted for corticosteroids such as beclomethasone, budesonide, and mometasone. These compounds share similar chemical properties, making the method transferable with minor adjustments^[28].
2. Pharmaceutical Formulations: The method can be used to quantify these corticosteroids in various formulations, including inhalers, nasal sprays, and topical creams. This ensures consistent quality and efficacy across different products.
3. Biological Samples: The method can also be applied to pharmacokinetic studies of other corticosteroids in biological matrices like blood, plasma, and urine. This is crucial for understanding the drug's absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion (ADME) profiles.

2. Application to Other Drug Classes:

1. Anti-inflammatory Drugs: The method can be extended to other anti-inflammatory drugs that require sensitive and accurate quantification. This includes non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) and immunosuppressants.
2. Hormones and Steroids: UPLC-MS can be used to analyze various hormones and steroids, providing valuable insights into their pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics.

Advances in UPLC-MS^[29,30]:

1. Enhanced Sensitivity and Resolution:

1. Technological Improvements: Recent advancements in UPLC-MS technology, such as the development of more sensitive detectors

and improved ionization techniques, have significantly enhanced the sensitivity and resolution of the method.

2. Solid-Core Technology: The use of solid-core particles in UPLC columns has improved column efficiency and peak shapes, leading to better separation and quantification of analytes.

2. Faster Analysis Times:

1. High-Pressure Systems: UPLC systems now operate at even higher pressures, allowing for faster flow rates and shorter analysis times without compromising resolution.
2. Miniaturization: The miniaturization of UPLC instruments has enabled high-throughput analyses, which is essential for drug discovery and screening.

3. Improved Data Quality:

1. Advanced Software: The integration of advanced data processing software has improved the accuracy and reproducibility of UPLC-MS analyses. These tools help in better peak integration, quantification, and identification of analytes.
2. Automated Optimization: Automated method optimization tools have simplified the process of developing and validating UPLC-MS methods, making it more accessible to laboratories with varying levels of expertise.

4. Broader Applications:

1. Metabolomics and Proteomics: UPLC-MS has expanded its applications to metabolomics and proteomics, providing detailed insights into the metabolic and protein profiles of biological samples.
2. Environmental Analysis: The method is also being used for the detection and quantification of environmental contaminants, such as

pesticides and pharmaceuticals in water and soil samples

CONCLUSION:

The analytical method developed for the quantification of fluticasone propionate utilizing Ultra Performance Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (UPLC-MS) exhibits considerable robustness, sensitivity, and precision, establishing it as a dependable instrument for pharmaceutical analysis. The method's adaptability to other corticosteroids and various drug classes highlights its potential for broader applications across different pharmaceutical formulations and biological matrices. Recent advancements in UPLC-MS technology have further enhanced the method's sensitivity, resolution, and efficiency, thereby permitting shorter analysis times and yielding improved data quality. These technological innovations also extend the method's applicability to fields such as metabolomics, proteomics, and environmental analysis, thereby demonstrating the versatility of UPLC-MS in addressing multifaceted analytical challenges.

In summary, the established guidelines and technological advancements ensure that this analytical approach not only satisfies current pharmaceutical analysis requirements but also lays the groundwork for future research and applications. This ultimately contributes to enhanced drug efficacy and safety, reinforcing the value of UPLC-MS in the field.

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